

When Gout Masquerades as Miliaria: A Case Report and Literature Review of an Unusual Cutaneous Manifestation

Ivanna Ocampo Carrasco¹, Eder F. Rios Bracamontes², Javier Perez Gutierrez³, Andrea G. Navarro Ortega⁴

¹Third-year Internal Medicine Resident, Hospital General de Zona 1, Villa de Alvarez, Colima, Department of Internal Medicine
Orcid: 0009-0007-4315-3954

²Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor of Internal Medicine, Hospital General de Zona 1, Villa de Alvarez, Colima, Department of Internal Medicine
Orcid: 0000-0002-4660-7372

³Dermatologist, Hospital General de Zona 1, Villa de Alvarez, Colima, Dermatology Department.

⁴Second-year Internal Medicine Resident, Hospital General de Zona 1, Villa de Alvarez, Colima, Department of Internal Medicine

ABSTRACT

We report a case of a 35-year-old male miner from Villa de Alvarez, Mexico, with a history of type 2 diabetes, hypertension, gout, and exogenous Cushing's syndrome due to prolonged dexamethasone use. He presented with disseminated skin lesions, initially misdiagnosed as severe acne, and later found to be cutaneous gout. Physical examination revealed moon face, oral candidiasis, and violaceous striae, with papular and nodular skin lesions on the extremities and abdomen, accompanied by joint involvement and tophi. Blood tests showed elevated uric acid levels (9.5 mg/dL). Skin biopsy confirmed the diagnosis of cutaneous gout with MSU crystal deposits. Treatment with allopurinol resulted in significant improvement in skin lesions. This case highlights the importance of early diagnosis and appropriate treatment in preventing the progression of gout, particularly in patients with unusual cutaneous manifestations.

KEYWORDS: Miliaria-like cutaneous gout, Tophaceous gout, Hyperuricemia, Grayish-white papules.

ARTICLE DETAILS

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CLINICAL CASE PRESENTATION

A case is reported of a 35-year-old male patient, a miner from Villa de Alvarez, Colima, Mexico, with a history of type 2 diabetes, systemic arterial hypertension, gout, and clinical signs of exogenous Cushing's syndrome due to the regular use of intramuscular dexamethasone for one and a half years. He reports the onset of skin lesions one year ago, initially on the upper extremities, later spreading to the lower extremities and abdomen, previously treated with clindamycin 300 mg every 12 hours for 3 weeks, with a prior suspicion of "severe disseminated acne."

Physical examination reveals a moon face, oral cavity with white plaques compatible with oropharyngeal candidiasis, cheilitis, abdomen with violaceous striae, and skin with disseminated monomorphic dermatosis characterized by indurated white-yellow papular and nodular lesions affecting the upper and lower extremities (extensor surfaces) and abdomen, along with joint involvement and tophi mainly in the metacarpophalangeal joints. Blood tests show uric acid at

9.5 mg/dL, creatinine at 1.83 mg/dL, and an electrolyte imbalance with hyponatremia, hypocalcemia, and hypokalemia.

A 4mm punch biopsy of the skin lesions and a 6mm x 4mm fusiform biopsy from the left upper extremity were taken. The dermatopathology report shows an eutrophic epidermis with orthokeratosis, dermis with amorphous material deposits containing crystals compatible with cutaneous gout, surrounded by multinucleated giant cells and a sparse mononuclear inflammatory infiltrate.

Treatment was initiated with an initial dose of 100 mg of allopurinol every 24 hours, gradually increasing to 300 mg. At the last follow-up, the dose was increased to 600 mg, with notable improvement in the lesions.

Literature review:

Gout is an inflammatory arthritis characterized by hyperuricemia (serum urate levels above 450 mmol/L or 7.0 mg/dL in men and 350 mmol/L or 6.0 mg/dL in women) and recurrent acute arthritis attacks triggered by the release of

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monosodium urate (MSU) crystals in synovial spaces. Its clinical course is typically described initially with years of asymptomatic hyperuricemia, followed by intermittent acute attacks, and eventually chronic arthritis with the formation of tophi, or collections of MSU crystals.

3% of patients diagnosed with gout develop the chronic tophaceous manifestation of the disease, usually in those who have not received treatment with uricosuric drugs. The first gout attack generally involves a single joint in the lower extremities, typically the first metatarsophalangeal joint in about 50% of cases, or the knee.(1,4)

Gout affects between 0.5% and 1% of the population, with an increasing incidence, likely related to demographic aging. In the United States, approximately 6.1 million adults, which is 2.5% of the adult population, have been diagnosed with gout. Its prevalence increases with age and is significantly higher in men than in women, with a ratio of 3 to 4 to 1. However, this gender difference diminishes in older individuals due to the decline in estrogen levels in women, as this hormone has a uricosuric effect. The increase in gout incidence and prevalence seems linked to population aging, as well as rising obesity rates and dietary changes. This condition has become the most common form of arthritis in men aged 30 to 50. Chronic tophaceous gout typically manifests after about a decade in untreated individuals, and between 12% and 35% of patients develop tophi.(3,5)

Tophi are granulomas formed by mononucleated and multinucleated macrophages surrounding a core of waste and MSU crystals. These are usually located in bursae, subcutaneous tissue over tendons, cartilage, and periarticular sites, mainly in the feet, ankles, knees, and fingers. They typically present as firm, yellowish-white subcutaneous nodules that are irregular and well-demarcated from surrounding tissue, usually located in joints. However, there has been a growing number of cases reported in the literature showing that gout can affect almost any part of the body, with the skin being one of the sites with the highest crystal precipitation after the joints. It is suggested that decreased urate solubility and increased crystal precipitation due to lower temperatures in the extremities, along with greater deposition of crystals in areas subjected to repetitive trauma, may play a role in the formation of intradermal tophi. (1)

Multiple clinical variants of tophaceous gout have been described, including cutaneous tophaceous lesions in different presentations. Types such as bullous, fungating, papular, ulcerative, pustular, post-traumatic, and nodular have been identified. However, among them, miliaria nodulosis or miliaria gout is an extremely rare manifestation, characterized by the presence of papules resembling milium cysts, distributed widely on the skin, containing a creamy white material with an erythematous base. These can present mild or moderate pain upon palpation or contact with hard surfaces, and may easily be confused with acne or folliculitis, leading to a delay in diagnosis and inappropriate treatment administration, as was the case with the patient in this report,

who initially received a diagnosis of severe acne and was given antibiotic treatment with no improvement. (2,3)

Some case reports mention that miliaria nodulosis or miliaria gout may be present without gout (joint involvement) or as an initial manifestation of gout, and it is generally associated with hyperuricemia. Although the exact pathophysiology of severe intradermal involvement is still unknown, some potential risk factors for the development of intradermal tophi described in reported cases include clinical obesity, chronic venous insufficiency, chronic kidney disease, chronic diuretic use, hypertension, and prolonged corticosteroid use, with the latter being a notable factor in the Mexican population, where these medications are easily accessible, as in the case presented in this review. (1,3)

Some complications that may arise in cases of severe cutaneous involvement due to tophaceous gout with skin infiltration, like miliaria gout, include multiple skin ulcers, panniculitis, and skin and soft tissue infections. In later stages, this can result in irreversible skin deformities. The possibility of gout coexisting with other rheumatologic diseases, such as rheumatoid arthritis, is low. A longitudinal study by Chiou A et al. reported that 6.1% of patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) develop gout, while 17% present hyperuricemia (>6.8 mg/dL). However, no significant association was found between these conditions and the severity of disease activity in RA. Additionally, a literature review on this pathological coexistence notes that in 75% of cases, gout appeared before the RA diagnosis.(7)

As part of the diagnostic approach, a skin biopsy is necessary when the clinical presentation is uncertain. Histopathological findings typically show deposits of amorphous crystalline material with negative birefringence of needle-shaped crystals on polarized microscopy. Tophi are often composed of eosinophilic amorphous material surrounded by granulomas of mononucleated or multinucleated macrophages in the dermis, with multiple deposits of crystals mixed with eosinophilic amorphous material surrounded by histiocytes in a palisade formation. (1,6)

The indicated treatment for tophaceous gout remains allopurinol, a drug that reduces uric acid production by competitively inhibiting xanthine oxidase, the enzyme responsible for converting xanthine and hypoxanthine into uric acid. Allopurinol is generally the first-line therapy, as it effectively reduces urate levels in all patients and has shown safety even in patients with chronic kidney disease, as is the case for a percentage of patients with this condition.

There are also surgical therapeutic options, which are less common but are used in cases of extensive involvement to decompress nerves, restore movement, stabilize joints, control infections, and improve aesthetic appearance. Curettage and debridement are the conventional surgical approaches for treating tophaceous gout. Moreover, soft tissue shaving has proven to be a promising alternative in the surgical treatment of this disease. (1)

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In our patient, allopurinol was successfully used to treat miliarial gout. Its administration resulted in progressive reduction in the size and number of the miliarial papules as the dosage was increased from 300 mg to 600 mg daily, and the patient continues to be followed up on an outpatient basis.

Gout is a metabolic disease that, although typically presenting with acute arthritis, can have unusual cutaneous manifestations, such as the miliaria-like form, which is often confused with other dermatological conditions like acne or folliculitis, delaying the diagnosis and appropriate treatment. The appearance of cutaneous tophi, especially in patients with a history of untreated hyperuricemia, can lead to severe complications if not promptly addressed. Skin biopsy is a crucial diagnostic tool in these cases, allowing for the identification of monosodium urate crystals and confirming the diagnosis.

Treatment with allopurinol remains the first-line therapy for reducing urate levels and preventing the formation of new crystals, demonstrating efficacy even in patients with comorbidities such as chronic kidney disease. In cases of severe cutaneous involvement, although less common, surgical options are useful for treating severe complications and improving the patient's quality of life. In the case presented, early intervention with allopurinol resulted in significant improvement in cutaneous lesions, highlighting the importance of timely diagnosis and treatment to prevent disease progression and complications.

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Image 1 and 2. Whitish papules corresponding to cutaneous tophi in a miliary-like pattern on the upper and lower extremities.

Image 3. Abdomen with a centripetal distribution of abdominal fat and violaceous striae as clinical manifestations of hypercortisolism.

Image 4. Skin biopsy at 10X magnification showing eosinophilic amorphous material corresponding to monosodium urate crystals surrounded by multinucleated giant cells forming granulomas.